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№ 1

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy,
innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid
ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
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- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

Elektron nashr,
448 sahifa, yanvar, 2025-yil.

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

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Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil
28-avgustdagi 360/5-son
qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar
asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop
etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy
ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga
texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari
bo'yicha "Muhandislik va
iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga
kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

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UNLOCKING OPPORTUNITIES IN UZBEKISTAN'S DERIVATIVES MARKETS: INSIGHTS FROM SOUTH KOREA AND INDIA

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Abstract: The research explores the current condition and the barriers to the development of derivatives markets in emerging economies within the context of Uzbekistan. The study analyzes case studies from India and South Korea, where derivatives markets underwent significant growth in the last decades. The results of the analysis reveal that implementing cutting-edge digital tools and technology, making markets more accessible, and creating favorable legal and regulatory environments for market participants are key to successfully attracting more investors and increasing the trading volume of derivative instruments. The findings also highlight the role of derivatives markets in stimulating economic growth, particularly, in emerging markets. The study concludes by providing actionable recommendations for regulators and policymakers to promote the development of derivatives markets in Uzbekistan and other emerging economies.

The information in this article is gathered through secondary research, primarily from scholarly articles, official pages of exchanges, government organizations, and reputable news sources.

Keywords: derivatives, emerging economies, South Korea, India, Uzbekistan, capital markets, financial innovation, economic growth.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekiston misolida rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyotlarda derivativ bozorlarining hozirgi holati va ularning rivojlanishidagi to'siqlarni o'rganadi. Tadqiqot so'nggi o'n yilliklarda derivativ bozorlarida sezilarli o'sishga erishgan Hindiston va Janubiy Koreya tajribalarini tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish, bozorlarga kirishni osonlashtirish hamda bozor ishtirokchilari uchun qulay huquqiy va tartibga solish muhitini yaratish muvaffaqiyatli rivojlanishning asosiy omillari ekanligini ko'rsatdi. Bundan tashqari, natijalar derivativ bozorlarining iqtisodiy o'sishga, ayniqsa, rivojlanayotgan bozorlar sharoitida, ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishini tasdiqlaydi. Tadqiqot O'zbekiston va boshqa rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda derivativ bozorlarini rivojlantirish uchun tartibga soluvchilar va siyosatchilar uchun aniq tavsiyalar bilan yakunlanadi.

Maqolada keltirilgan ma'lumotlar asosan ilmiy maqolalar, fond birjalari, hukumat tashkilotlari va ishonchli axborot manbalarining rasmiy sahifalaridan olingan ikkilamchi tadqiqotlarga asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar: derivativlar, rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyotlar, Janubiy Koreya, Hindiston, O'zbekiston, kapital bozorlar, moliyaviy innovatsiyalar, iqtisodiy o'sish

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматривается текущее состояние и барьеры на пути развития рынков деривативов в развивающихся экономиках на примере Узбекистана. Анализируются кейсы Индии и Южной Кореи, где рынки деривативов значительно выросли за последние десятилетия. Результаты исследования показывают, что внедрение передовых цифровых технологий, упрощение доступа к рынку и создание благоприятной правовой и регулирующей среды для участников рынка являются ключевыми факторами успешного привлечения инвесторов и увеличения объемов торгов деривативами. Кроме того, исследование подтверждает важную роль рынков деривативов в стимулировании экономического роста, особенно в развивающихся странах. В заключении представлены практические рекомендации для регуляторов и политиков по развитию рынков деривативов в Узбекистане и других развивающихся экономиках.

Информация в данной статье основана на вторичных источниках, включая научные статьи, официальные сайты бирж, государственных организаций и авторитетных новостных агентств.

Ключевые слова: Деривативы, развивающиеся экономики, Южная Корея, Индия, Узбекистан, рынки капитала, финансовые инновации, экономический рост.

INTRODUCTION

The derivatives market plays a crucial role in enhancing a country's financial system and fostering economic growth, making it a significant area of research for many years. The rising demand for alternative investments, such as those in emerging markets and unconventional asset classes, has led to greater interest in using derivative instruments. These instruments help hedge against the heightened risks associated with the potential for higher yields (Hong Vo et al., 2019).

In both emerging and developed markets, derivatives are widely used for hedging risks associated with foreign exchange exposure, changes in interest rates, and commodity prices. Recognizing the importance of derivatives in integrating into global finance, policymakers and governments in emerging economies are actively making structural reforms to their financial markets to address issues hindering the growth of derivatives markets (Jobst, 2008).

The purpose of this research is to investigate the role of derivatives in emerging economies and examine the current state of Uzbekistan's financial markets. The report aims to learn comparative cases from South Korea and India to provide recommendations on addressing challenges and opportunities in the capital markets of Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW OF THE TOPIC

2.1 Financial Development and Economic Growth

Research studies, both empirical and theoretical, have concluded that developed financial markets directly contribute to a country's economic growth by fostering capital accumulation and ensuring that capital is employed efficiently within the economy (Ang, 2008). The results of a study conducted on 83 emerging economies by Sarwar et al. (2020) indicate a significant relationship between the development of financial markets and the economic growth of these emerging economies. Their findings align with an earlier study done by Hassan, Sanchez and Yu (2011) which argues that the efficiency of the financial system stimulates economic growth in low and middle-income countries. A key indicator of financial development is "financial depth," which measures the liquidity and volume of the financial system relative to the country's GDP. Derivatives play an important role in this aspect. According to Haiss and Sammer (2010), there are three channels – volume, efficiency, and risk – through which derivatives function as a nexus between the financial system and economic growth.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the study, the author used scientific abstraction, analysis and synthesis, comparative analysis, and observation methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

2.2 The Role of Derivatives in Financial Development

Firstly, derivatives markets promote a faster accumulation of capital by allowing market participants to allocate more resources through savings mobilization and investment in risky projects in a diversified portfolio. Secondly, derivatives help improve efficiency in the economy by replacing cash trades, transferring information, and facilitating risk management. To illustrate this point, firms can access cheaper funding from foreign or domestic capital markets regardless of the currency denomination using interest swaps. Finally, the risk channel suggests that derivatives may hinder economic growth by encouraging speculation on the underlying, adding “unnecessary risk” to the market. However, according to Jobst (2008), derivatives serve as an information channel conveying information about future prices, ultimately leading to a decrease in spot price volatility based on his study on emerging economies. Şendeniz-Yüncü, Akdeniz, and Aydoğan (2017) also claim that the derivatives allow firms to share risks for market-traded commodities and thus take projects with a higher risk, subsequently leading to an economic boost.

2.3 Barriers to Developing Derivative Markets in Emerging Economies

Şendeniz-Yüncü, Akdeniz, and Aydoğan (2017) state that in high-income countries, economic growth results in a more developed futures market. Conversely, in countries with low real GDP per capita, the development of the futures market fosters economic growth. Therefore, the impact of the derivatives market is even more profound in the context of emerging markets. However, emerging economies encounter several obstacles that impede the development of their derivatives markets. According to Jobst (2008), these obstacles include illiquid cash markets and a lack of trading infrastructure. He adds that the inadequacy of legal and regulatory frameworks also negatively affects the evolution of derivatives markets. In the case of equity derivatives, due to the necessity of liquid collateral and pricing benchmarks, derivatives trading usually requires huge trading volumes in cash markets for efficient price formation. Some Asian equity markets exhibit low liquidity due to transparency and corporate governance issues, leading to information asymmetry in the market. This results in wide bid-ask spreads and limits on trading activities. Implementing structural reforms to their financial markets is important to address issues hindering the growth of derivatives markets in these emerging economies.

2.4 Case of the Indian Derivatives Market

The introduction of Index futures at the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) in 2000 and later the National Stock Exchange (NSE) marked the commencement of derivative trading in the Indian market. Since then, the volume in terms of value and number of derivative contracts has increased considerably. There are a number of factors that contributed to the “explosive growth” of the Indian equity derivatives market. First, consistent with the IOSCO principles, the regulatory framework in India addressed issues associated with protecting investors, improving market efficiency, and ensuring financial integrity (Vashishtha and Kumar, 2010) (picture 1).

Picture 1. Historical business growth of equity derivatives at NSE between 2000 and 2024.

Source: NSE market data.

Implementing an advanced clearing and settlement system to the underlying equity market also played a key role in achieving high trading volumes and an efficient formation of prices in India’s exchange-traded

derivative market. For instance, the settlement and clearing cycle was shortened to T+1 and T+2 through gradual reformations such as an electronic transfer of securities and automation of settlements. These improvements led to reduced delays and operational errors alongside facilitating the clearing process (Jobst, 2008).

Additionally, India reviewed the prohibitions on short-selling and working on new regulations regarding the registration process of foreign institutional investors, and the Securities Exchange Board of India published new guidelines on short-selling in 2007 after a ban on the practice since the beginning of the 2000s (Jain and Jain, 2015). While short-selling across all categories, including equity futures and options is allowed in India, the framework restricts “naked short-selling” and requires traders to disclose their short positions to prevent these activities from negatively impacting liquidity by causing downward pressure in the market (Fohlin, Lu and Zhou, 2022).

Case of the South Korean Derivatives Market

The trading of derivative instruments across various categories—such as interest rate, equity, commodities, FOREX, and credit—has rapidly expanded in Asian exchanges. South Korea, along with India, is primarily responsible for the significant increase in trading volume within the Asia-Pacific region (Acworth, 2019). South Korea is one of the few Asian countries where derivative trading surpassed the capitalization of cash and equity trading. Furthermore, after merging with the Korean Stock Exchange in 2004 to form the Korean Exchange (KRX), the Korean Futures Exchange (KOFEX) became one of the largest futures exchanges globally by trading volume (Jobst, 2008). A variety of factors contributed to the remarkable growth of the derivatives market in the country (picture 2).

Picture 2. KOSPI 200 Futures historical price change from 2003 to 2024.

Source: Investing.com

According to Webb (2022), one of the distinctive features of the Korean derivatives market is its investor base. Unlike many other markets, the Korean derivatives market is dominated by retail investors rather than institutional investors. This is due to the simplicity of derivative products available to individual traders, along with low transaction costs and margin requirements in KOFEX. Another important factor could be South Korea’s strong emphasis on improving the financial literacy and expertise of both the general public and professionals. For example, KRX Academy offers comprehensive learning programs on investment topics, including derivatives, capital markets, and foreign exchange risk. It also provides simulated trading platforms for short-selling and derivatives trading. Infrastructure is another contributing aspect. South Korea implemented the use of internet-based trading platforms for its retail investors which enhanced market accessibility.

3.1 The current state of financial markets in Uzbekistan

While Uzbekistan transitioned from a command economy to a free market economy upon gaining independence, the qualities of a capitalist economy have only begun to take shape in recent years. Thus, experts believe that the liquidity of the financial markets of Uzbekistan is yet insufficient mainly due to the lack of involvement among the general public and institutions. To illustrate, legal entities account for more than two-thirds of the investors by transaction volume according to the latest figures provided by the RSE “Toshkent”. Furthermore, the application of modern financial tools like derivatives instruments is limited, which creates barriers for businesses to enhance investor confidence and attract foreign investment (Shakirov, 2022). In 2022, the Uzbekistan Republican Currency Exchange (UzRCE) introduced currency futures, with the first

transaction for buying and selling currency futures occurring in November, aimed at hedging and speculation purposes. Currently, the only type of currency futures available in the UzRCE derivatives market is futures contracts based on the US dollar exchange rate against the UZS as the underlying asset. However, after the first transaction, there were only a few currency futures transactions in the currency market, the last of which took place in 2023, highlighting the need for actions to promote further growth.

Recent developments in Uzbekistan's financial markets

The country has been taking notable steps to transform its financial landscape. In September 2023 the Central Bank of Uzbekistan held a meeting with the representatives of the International Swaps and Derivatives Association (ISDA) in London to address the issues related to developing derivative instruments and attracting foreign investment to the financial markets. In the meeting, EBRD agreed to provide technical assistance such as conducting gap analysis and preparing an inception report before working on the legal and regulatory framework. This collaboration aims to create an efficient and favorable legal framework for issuing, trading, and regulating derivative instruments (CBU, 2023). Moreover, Uzbekistan's capital markets have undergone significant amendments, which are crucial for the successful development of derivative markets. According to Presidential Decree No. 90, individuals are not required to pay dividend taxes, and a mobile app has been created to allow them to participate in the market remotely. Foreign banks and financial intermediaries can underwrite local securities without getting licensed in Uzbekistan. Presidential Decree No. 6207 (2021) emphasizes the necessity of developing new financial products and instruments, as well as implementing IT solutions to enhance the capital market infrastructure. Uzbekistan is also working on introducing mortgage-based securities to take its financial transformation to a next level (Daryo.uz, 2024). While these actions demonstrate the country's commitment to improving its financial markets, it is crucial to continually learn and adopt global best practices.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the above analysis, here are some recommendations for market development in Uzbekistan:

Financial education. Given that the derivatives market is still in its early stages of development, it is essential to promote educational programs on capital markets, specifically focusing on derivatives for retail investors. This can be achieved by introducing professional certification programs in the local language to ensure accessibility for a wider audience. Additionally, establishing partnerships with global financial institutions to provide education on the latest financial technologies and tools should be considered. It is important to tailor these programs to align with local capital market conditions, as concepts that work in other regions may not be suitable for the unique characteristics of the local market. To target the younger generation, gamified learning tools, and trading simulations can be used. KRX Education is a perfect example of this.

Digital transformation. Improving digital platforms for trading derivatives and underlying assets is essential for attracting a broader investor base. Tools that are accessible to less tech-savvy investors should also be taken into consideration. These digital solutions should include basic financial advice, educational content, and interactive investor platforms to boost investor confidence and engagement. Digitally transforming the capital markets can reduce the time and costs spent on settlement and processing, ultimately improving market efficiency. For example, BSE's trading platform can process half a million orders per second thanks to its advanced network provided by HCL and Cisco. It uses a trading engine offered by Deutsche Boerse and is considered the fastest in Asia with its response time being in microseconds (MySQL, 2019).

Regulatory compliance. Sophisticated derivatives require prudential legal and regulatory frameworks, including laws specifically on derivatives (Jobst, 2008). As new tools and instruments are introduced to the market, regulating speculative activities and building a robust legal and regulatory framework become increasingly important. International best practices should be observed and adopted to enhance transparency in the market.

The recommendations provided in this research can help policymakers address the systematic barriers Uzbekistan's financial markets face, promoting financial innovation and unlocking its financial potential.

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Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 1

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"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

